

ROLE OF MASS MEDIA ON POLITICAL ACCOUNTABILITY IN SOMALIA.

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the role of mass media on political accountability in Somalia. Worldwide there has been a drive to make governments more accountable to the needs of citizens. Though there is widespread consensus on the need to improve accountability it is much less clear what mechanisms might be used to achieve this end. This study suggests that a free and independent press working in conjunction with democratic institutions can make governments more responsive to the needs of citizens. Accountability happens when parliament is fully functional and elections process is freely and fair. These prerequisites require respect of freedom of expression, fair journalism, citizen raise voice and participate in political discourse. A free and independent media should be viewed as a requisite and integral part of representative democracy. Study was guided by the following research questions; what is the role of social media on political accountability in Somalia? What is the role of Broadcast media on political accountability in Somalia? How media ownership effect political accountability in Somalia? The researcher proposed the study methodology including research design which was descriptive design, cross sectional data collecting method, using a self-administered questionnaire that was distributed to a sample of 80. The sample size was determined by using Slovene`s formula for sample-size determination. The data collected using questionnaire and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social sciences (SPSS) version 20 and spreadsheet excel. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze data using frequencies and percentages. A number of recommendations were made after the study to government institutions, media organizations and society at large.

INTRODUCTION

1.0 Introduction

This Section introduces the study as a whole. It consists of background of the study, problem statement, objectives of the study, research questions, significance of the study, scope of the study, operational definitions of key terms and conceptual framework in relation to analyzing the role of mass media on political accountability in Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.1 Background of the study

Mass media can play a key role in enabling citizens to monitor the actions of incumbents and use information in their voting decisions. This can lead to government which is more accountable and responsive to its citizens' needs. It is assumed that when people have information they are more knowledgeable and therefore, they act in a better way compared to those without information (Besley et al, 2002)

The ability of the citizens to hold governments, elected representatives and other power holders accountable has been widely regarded as one of the crucial components and cornerstones of democracy. According to democratic theory, accountability – commonly understood as the obligation of the public officials to inform and justify their decisions in front of the electorate, and the capacity of the public or responsible institutions to sanction their behavior – is one of the main measures of to the quality of democratic governance and is regarded as the key mechanism in improving surveillance over officeholders, constraining their exercise of power and raising the overall governmental effectiveness. As Schmitter (2007: 134) puts it, “the more accountable a real-existing democracy is, the higher will be the quality of its performance”(Štětka, 2012).

The primary political accountability mechanism is free and fair elections. Other mechanisms are prosecution, resignation, sacking and impeachment. For this to be effective there is a need for information to be provided by the actor concerning his/her actions both acted and intended in a timely manner. It should be reliable and sufficient.

When the information is provided, there should be a proper debate on that information which should provide sufficient opportunity for the forum to pose questions, for the actor to explain his conduct and enough time to hear both sides. The judgment procedure should be based on whether the forum is independent, the forum is biased, the standards are clear, the facts warrant the judgment and whether the sanctions are proportionate. The media delivers this information through outlets such as: newspapers, magazines, radio and television stations, film and digital and social media. One segment of this information is politics. Stromberg (2015) says that the key role of information in politics is to help voters elect leaders who will give them the most utility. This increases the responsiveness of voters to the quality of politicians which improves political selection and incentives and eventually policy and welfare (Wanjiku, 2021).

Globally many studies from Latin America and Europe have proved this assumption to great extent. According to Ferraz and Finan (2007), the media coverage on corruption audit reports from various municipalities in Brazil, reduced the implicated incumbent mayors' re-election chances by 17.8% while it increased the likelihood of the non-implicated mayors' re-election by 18%. In municipalities with a radio station, the implicated mayors' chances of re-election were reduced by 52% (Wanjiku, 2021).

In Colombia, growth of media outlets, which represented a new source of information about local and national politics, affected the voter turnout by about 19% on the presidential election from 47.5% in 1994 to 65.02% in 2010. Increase of one radio station was associated with 1.1% increase in voter turnout. The research indicated that the work of the media if strong, can affect how the government deals with expenditure. It showed that the government of Colombia was able to increase investment expenditure from 41% in 1994 to about 85% of the total expenditures in 2010. On political competition, the report showed that, expanding media space doesn't only increase citizens' participation in politics but also improves political competition where the influence of the dominant parties: Liberal and Conservative was reduced. This is from about 70% in 1994 to about 30% in 2010, with non-victorious parties getting an average of 61.7% of the 102 assigned seats in the Senate

up from 13.7% in 1994. The number of radio stations increased from 210 in 1994 to 1100 in 2010 (Wanjiku, 2021).

In Africa the provision of section 22 of the 1999 Constitution of Nigeria places an obligation on the press to uphold the responsibility and accountability of government to the people. Thus, democracy can hardly survive and achieve its yearnings in any society where there is no accountability, transparency and the inclusion of the majority of the people in governance and in determining the input into the process of development; all of which are guaranteed through a free and independent media. Therefore, the responsibility of the media is in holding the government accountable to the people is fundamental to the overall success of democracy (Msughter, 2019).

In a democratic environment, the media's purpose extends beyond the basic functions of information, education and entertainment. The media also has the responsibility of sustaining and nourishing the ideals of democratic ethos and to constantly assure and guarantee the protection of freedom of individuals and that of the media themselves, which is the heart of popular participation in liberal democracies. The press can promote democracy by educating voters, protecting human rights, promoting tolerance among various social groups and ensuring that government is transparent and accountable, etc. (Msughter, 2019).

For a developing country like Nigeria, which still reels with voter's apathy, buying of votes, snatching of ballot boxes and asterism, the involvement of the media becomes even more important. The backward and ignorance of the poor should make the media emboldened regarding its responsibility to bring them modern ideas for eliminating poverty and other social evils like it's doing in reporting issues regarding corruption (Msughter, 2019).

In Somalia the society arguably ranks among the most media literate in Africa. While much divides a deeply fractured, war-torn and now drought-stricken and famine-stricken country, an ancient love of poetry and a common language unite it. So, throughout recent history, has an avid Consumption of news and information. Obtaining information and assessing its trustworthiness has, in this traditionally pastoralist and nomadic society, always shaped not just politics, society and culture, but the odds of survival (Hassan, 2018).

During the reign of Somalia's military ruler, Mohamed Siyad Barre (1969-1991), the government was in total control of the media. The ministry of information had Broadcasting Department which ran Radio Mogadishu and Radio Hargeisa. The only daily newspaper, October Star, was state-run and published in English, Arabic, Italian and Somali. There was also the Somali National News Agency (SONNA) was the source of official information to international news agencies. During the early days of the bloody civil war, many radio stations and newspapers opened, but due to the raging war in many parts of the country they had to affiliate themselves with clans or get out of business (Hassan, 2018).

From 1996, the Somali local media started to become more independent from clan affiliation, while large percentage of their audiences began to ignore propaganda and look for real and constructive news sources. On their part, media owners started looked for qualified journalist and moving away from hiring their kinsmen to do the job. Radio plays a dominant role in Somalia's media landscape, due to the oral culture of the Somalis, the inexpensive nature of the medium as well as the high illiteracy rates in the country. The print and TV sectors are weak and radio is by far the dominant medium. There more than 56 radio-stations in the country including radio Mogadishu which was re launched in 2001 after the state collapse in 1991 and Radio Hargeisa in the Self-declared Republic of Somaliland (Hassan, 2018).

After the state collapse, Somalia was mapped into three sub sections namely; South Central, Puntland and Somaliland. South Central Somalia has seen the mushrooming of media houses, mainly radio stations. These operate under constant threats, with bans, intense fighting and arrest of journalists (mainly from Al-Shabab and the FGS). This led to the shutting down of a number of radio stations. Likewise, radio is the main medium in Puntland. Although the semi-autonomous region's media is seen to be independent, the authorities there sustain a strong control over it. This is in contrast to the lack of a strong central authority to exert its control over the media in South Central region. The media landscape in the breakaway Somaliland is very different from the other two regions. Newspapers flourished in the breakaway region and have played a considerable role in the fostering of democracy and maintaining a strong sense of self-rule.

1.2 Problem statement

While freedom of information is a key resource for holding the government to account, freedom of the media has come under threat from all sides in ongoing fight between governmental forces and various non-state armed groups. Killing and intimidating of journalists and media organizations from Al-shabab (Islamic armed group) and the federal government and regional authorities have used a wide range of tactics to compel journalists to cover key issues in a way authorities deem acceptable. These include arbitrary arrests and forced closures of media outlets, threats, harassment, and occasionally the filing of criminal charges. These threats and attacks against journalists are undermining Somalis' rights to basic and accurate information as media organizations censor themselves to survive which in turn makes impossible for the citizens to hold their leaders accountable. Ongoing armed conflict, insecurity, lack of state protection, and recurring humanitarian crises exposed Somali civilians to serious abuse. However, Somalia is glaring example of the need for improved accountability, as the political history of the country has been plagued by bad governance, gross violations of human rights, gender violence, dehumanizing poverty, high-level corruption and economic stagnation.

1.3 Objectives of the study

1.3.1 General objective

The general objective of the study is to identify the role of mass media on political accountability in Somalia.

1.3.2 Specific objectives

- To find out the role of social media on political accountability in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- To determine the role of Broadcast media on political accountability in Mogadishu, Somalia.
- To assess ways in which media ownership effects political accountability in Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.4 Research questions

1. What is the role of social media on political accountability in Somalia?
2. What is the role of Broadcast media on political accountability in Somalia?
3. How media ownership effect political accountability in Somalia?

1.5 Significance of the study

This study provides information of the role of Somali media on political accountability and tries to lighten up the relationship between the government of Somalia and the media. This study is useful for future researchers because it acts as a guideline for them to follow in the subsequent studies related to the same problem under investigation and also a source of information to refer as a literature. The study has also increased understanding the wide extent to which media involves in influencing on political accountability in Somalia, the challenges faced by the media and the study has put forward suggestions on what should be done by the media in overcoming the challenges faced in reporting and dissemination of information before the public on issues of political accountability in Somalia. Additionally the study is to act as a guiding framework for media institutions in Somalia. The study set framework towards reminding policy makers to make policies that will protect the independence of the media in ensuring strong political accountability in Somalia.

1.6 Scope of the study

1.6.1 Content scope

The study will be concentrated on the role of mass media on political accountability in Somalia; the study will specifically focus on the role of social media, broadcast media and media ownership on political accountability.

1.6.2 Geographical scope

The study will be conducted in Mogadishu Somalia.

1.6.3 Time scope

The study focuses particularly the president Mohamed Abdullahi Mohamed Farmajo's regime (8 February 2017-8 February 2021) and one year and three months of illegal and unconstitutional extension period. This regime's period seems to be time where Somali media faced the most challenges since the military regime. The government oppresses media that critics its actions by torturing journalists, arbitrary arrestments and closing media outlets such as Mustaqbal media and etc. other techniques government used to deviate media from its watchdog function include by promising media organization owner(s) money or job opportunities and establishing government paid individuals to harass opponents of government these individuals known as Cayayanka Baraha Bulshada (CBB). The study will be conducted in between July to September 2022.

1.7 Operational definitions of key terms

Media: means of communication, as radio and television, newspapers, and magazines, which reach or influence people widely (Welle, 2009).

Accountability: is the obligation of an individual or organization to account for its activities, accept responsibility for them and to disclose the results in a transparent manner (Wanjiku, 2021).

Political accountability: refers to the responsibility or obligation of government officials to act in the best interest of society or face consequences (Wanjiku, 2021).

Social media are defined as "a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of user-generated content" (kaplan and Haenlein, 2010).

Broadcast media: describes the traditional forms of media that include television and radio.

Ownership in relation to the media refers to the proprietorship rights which someone, a group of persons or an institution, exercises over a media establishment (Kate Azuka Omenugha et al, 2013).

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

This Section focuses on the review of related literature on this study, which is about the role of mass media on political accountability in Somalia. Firstly it covers a discussion on role of social media on political accountability, secondly it describes role of broadcast media on political accountability and lastly ways media ownership effects political accountability.

2.1 Role of social media on political accountability

By now, a world without the internet is unimaginable. Connecting billions of people worldwide, the internet is a core pillar of the modern information society. The global internet penetration rate is 59 percent, with Northern Europe ranking first with a 95 percent internet penetration rate among the population. The countries with the highest internet penetration rate worldwide are the UAE, Denmark, and South Korea. At the opposite end of the spectrum is North Korea with virtually no online usage penetration among the general population, ranking last worldwide. As of 2019, Asia was the region with the largest number of online users – over 2.3 billion at the latest count. Europe was ranked second with almost 728 million internet users (johnson, 2022)

Social media usage is one of the most popular online activities. In 2020, over 3.6 billion people were using social media worldwide, a number projected to increase to almost 4.41 billion in 2025. Social networking is one of the most popular digital activities worldwide and it is no surprise that social networking penetration across all regions is constantly increasing. As of January 2020, the global social media usage rate stood at 49 percent. This figure is anticipated to grow as lesser developed digital markets catch up with other regions when it comes to infrastructure development and the availability of cheap mobile devices. In fact, most of social media's global growth is driven by the increasing usage of mobile devices. Mobile-first market Eastern Asia topped the global ranking of mobile social networking penetration, followed by established digital powerhouses such as the Americas and Northern Europe (Statista Research Department, 2022)

Social media platforms had a staggering number of users and reached out to various citizens around the globe regardless of class, gender, ethnicity or location. They give everyone the chance to express their own views, interact with existing information, mobilize others and gain support for their causes and initiatives. This ability to mobilize had an effect on both politics and accountability and resulted in various political movements throughout the globe. For instance, in Nigeria social media has made it possible not only to challenge public officials' integrity but also their personal values and belief system, which often relied on their consciences. Dialog is a major channel of public accountability; this dialog is often conducted through critical debate about government actions. Dialogue is becoming more effective with the spread of media and new technologies that facilitated public debates and created a space where citizens can share their agreement or criticism for government policies and actions, question officials, and request justifications for their actions (Usman et al., 2020).

Officials in modern times often have their own Facebook and twitter pages where they deal directly with the public and answer their questions. This has exceeded the usual mediating mechanisms that have always existed between the public and civil servants like the newspaper, the ombudsman and the parliament. However, these virtual channels have not been treated similarly by all officials and there is still a lot of improvement to be made in this regard to provide more space for people to interact. Social media thus provides a space for dialog between government and citizens, and may result in public outrage requiring a higher pace of government responsiveness to the public interest and failure to do so. Public accountability over social media platforms is not often perceived in the same way by the public. Politicians can be questioned and held accountable for their actions only when citizens do not fear the consequences of criticizing them on the virtual space (Usman et al., 2020).

Therefore, the perception of public accountability, whether it is against politicians or administrative officials in the age of social media, depends primarily on where power is focused and what degree of freedom is granted to the people to voice their concerns, challenge government actions and organize pressure groups.

Furthermore, it has been argued that SNS reduce barriers to collective action facilitating the coordination of political movements and promoting protests and uprisings, so that—after the “Arab Spring”—several scholars speculated on the role of the Internet and SNS in undermining authoritarian regimes (Ceron, 2017).

It comes as no surprise that autocratic leaders frequently attempt to engage in censorship saying that these online comments are “dangerous” and damaging for the status quo. This debate immediately flows from the academic realm to the real world, considering that the Turkish premier Erdogan has repeatedly tried to limit Internet access and to switch-off SNS in order to prevent the circulation of information online (Ceron, 2017).

However, even in democratic political systems, politicians such as former New York mayor Michael Bloomberg have blamed SNS for allowing citizens to hamper decisions made by political institutions, thereby thwarting governance in the democratic polity. So, do social media lead to a political revolution? If we had to stick to the opinions and the censorious behavior of such prominent political leaders, the answer would be yes. The story, however, is probably more complex and less univocal than this. Indeed, other scholars hold a more skeptical view. On the one hand, they claim that online communities can produce undesired consequences for the democratic polity given that they radicalize (rather than moderate) the positions of their users becoming a source of ideological lock-ins (Ceron, 2017).

Some scholars argued that social media provide an opportunity to foster the transparency of governments and to strengthen the interaction between citizens and public administrations. As for transparency, scholars underlined how social media give to politicians and bureaucrats the opportunity to be accountable for their actions in the platforms preferred by citizens. In particular, public entities could disseminate information concerning their activities, allowing citizens to monitor public expenditure and to formulate judgments on public services. (Ceron, 2017)

The social media in the public sphere accountability posits that the social media can directly hold those in power/ government to account by acting as watchdogs over leaders. It provides a platform for robust, constructive public dialogue in the public sphere. It provides a platform for those in power to answer for their action and improve participation.

The social media creates new ways of working through online collaboration across government departments and with citizens. This has led to changes in the way government operates and develops policy (Jimada, 2019).

2.2 Role of broadcast media on political accountability

The role of broadcast media in deepening democracy cannot be undermined in any sense whatsoever. The media is a term used to denote a section of the media specifically envisioned and designed to reach a very large audience such as the population of a nation state. Media has to do with the television, radio, newspapers, magazines, books and the internet. Broadcast media being the main focus on the other hand can be defined as “the dissemination of message through transmission over radio and television that provides for reception by the public as opposed to narrow-casting” (SARFO et al., 2017).

A part from advancing public knowledge, the news media’s main mission is to keep the society aware of the public concern and interest. Each media has a message it wants to convey to the public in order to fulfill their role in the society, such as to provide relevant information, educate, promote democratic values such as the rule of law, good governance, transparency and accountability, entertain and impart knowledge. They regularly cover all sorts of issues such as health, music, fine art, crime, sport, entertainment, political events among others. Tosanisunmi (2004) has observed that the mass media educate, inform and entertain beyond these functions as they also persuade and catalyze for social mobilization. Free press, public’s right to be informed, change and retain of government in electoral processes, just to mention a few are all true reflections of democracy (SARFO et al., 2017).

Broadcasting retains a position of enormous influence over social, cultural, and political life in nearly all parts of the world. Although it might reasonably be concluded that high income people can obtain much of their information and media over the Internet, this is certainly not the case in lower and lower middle income groups. Here radio and television (only a small proportion watch home satellite) are the primary media outlets. Given that communal viewing and listening (radio and television are the media with the greatest reach, especially among poor people) are far more common in poor countries than in wealthy ones, the actual proportion of the population that consumes radio and television is likely to be considerably higher than

the proportion that owns a set. Despite the rapid expansion of the Internet, television has maintained its massive appeal to viewers worldwide (Buckley et al., n.d.).

2.3 Effects of media ownership on political accountability

Independent media is the lifeblood for a domestic accountable and transparent government and democracy. The Media is taken as one of the strongest pillars in enforcing and influencing public accountability either through vertical or horizontal accountability mechanisms. The media is one of the fundamental pillars that every democratic society would leave without. In essence any developing democracy requires the media industry through which the citizens are empowered in understanding what their government does in terms of policy making, political decisions, security and public service delivery. The significance of the media in holding the government accountable for its decisions and actions represents social growth and development (Chacha, 2014).

This objective examines how ownership of the media affects the media in the performance of their watchdog role on government. The media as a fourth estate; recognizing the media's watchdog role over the other arms of government. Indeed, many social science scholars have argued that the media's ability to hold government and other sections of society accountable to the public is the main justification for the unfettered media freedom found in many liberal democratic constitutions around the world. Accountability is central to democratic governance as it gives citizens, civil society, and the private sector the ability to scrutinize public institutions and governments and to hold them to account. The media can be a powerful source of change in both developed and undeveloped worlds if at all its ownership targets the public accountability and achieving the media watchdog function.

Undoubtedly, one of the most important actors in the push for accountability is the media. However, there is an important distinction that needs to be made between the state owned media, and a free and independent press. We focus on how media ownership affects political accountability, ways in which private and state owned media perform their watchdog function holding governments accountable and which media organization performs better in this function.

The independent private media can conduct investigations to uncover corruption and provide a forum for discussing corruption and mobilizing anti-corruption reforms (Asomah, 2020).

Generally, independent and free media sources perform the role of watchdog over governmental actors as they report on instances of abuse of power such as corruption. Some have even taken to comparing the press to a house-fly based on its habit of showing up when things start stinking. Ultimately, an independent media is an ally of citizens in a democracy as it asks critical questions of politicians on behalf of the entire community that demands them to provide information on recent developments and accompanying justifications for their actions. When discussing the role of the media in a democracy Meiklejohn argued that: “democracy is based on the notion of popular sovereignty. This requires that citizens be well informed if they are to participate in the political process and effectively play their role as the ultimate decision makers. A free and diverse press allows them to perceive a variegated view of issues on the basis of which they can make informed political decisions” (Butler, 2013).

Furthermore, the media provides a market place for ideas whereby different views and claims can be made, but are then subjected to contestation which increases the chance for the truth to emerge and shape politics. In simple terms, the media educates the population about ongoing political developments, provides a forum for civic engagement, and works to promote accountability by demanding answers from political actors. That being said, the media is engaged in a form of vertical accountability that lacks power of enforcement on those determined to have abused their power. The media can only provide public disapproval, and are thus reliant on actors such as the judiciary (an equal to the executive) to sanction wrongdoing (Butler, 2013). State owned media in an authoritarian regime often performs the function of cheerleader and provides a forum for distribution of propaganda materials for the ruling regime. Furthermore, neutrality by the state owned media is not enough, as they are encouraged to attack and refute those who criticize the government. This practice is obviously a result of the fact that the government as owner of the organization possesses the ability to hire and fire journalists, and is the main means of economic support (Butler, 2013).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 Introduction

This Section shows a detailed description of selected methods which includes: research design, study population, sample size, sampling procedure/ technique, data collection method, and data quality control and analyses.

3.1 Research design

The study was being cross sectional in design. The study was also being quantitative in design.

3.2 Study population

The study consists of 100 target populations of civil society, politicians, and private and public media. The researcher selected those groups because they have information, facts and experience of the role of media on the political accountability. All these are most important sources that i could get reliable information about the study.

3.3 Sample size and Data Collection method

the researcher used non probability/purposive sampling which mean to select the respondents intentionally. The data collected using Questionnaire tool.

The sample size was determined by using Slovene`s formula for sample-size determination:

Where: $n = N / (1 + (N * e^2))$,

N = Total Population (100)

n = Sample size

e = is errors at 0.05^2

Substituting into the formula, $n = 100 / (1 + 100(0.0025)) = 80$

Table: 3. 1 Sample size

No	Respondents	Sample size
1	Private media	25
2	Public media	20
3	Politicians	20
4	Civil society	15
5	Total	<u>80</u>

Source: Primary Data, 2022

3.4 The validity of data

Validity of the study will assured through expert knowledge and research instrument is valid and it actually measures what it is supposed to measure.

3.5 Data analysis

Data was analyzed using statistical package for social science – SPSS. Descriptive analysis was done and then frequency tables and charts were used in order to present study results. In this study, the Researcher was employed Mean to analyze the Results of Questionnaire using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS).

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

4.0 Introduction

This study investigated the role of mass media on political accountability in Somalia, Data collected from the respondents using questionnaire and it was analyzed using descriptive statistics through special software called Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) and spreadsheet. This Section presents the results of the analyses in both tables containing the type of responses, its frequencies, percentages and cumulative percentages.

Thus, this Section presents data analysis of all answers given by the respondents to the asked questions in the questionnaire. Each question has a table . Each table showed the indicator, the frequency, the percentage, and the cumulative percent.

This descriptive analysis contained the results obtained from **80** questionnaires distributed from those respondents. According to the prior objectives of the research, this Section concentrates to interpret the research findings.

4.1 Demographic of the Respondents

With the use of SPSS, this theme presents data about the demographic variables of the main population sample. The research relied on the accounts given by 80 people, men and women. This data specifically covers variables such as Gender, Age, Marital Status, Educational level and Experience as summarized in Tables and figures 4.1.1- 4.1.5.

Table: 4.1.1 Gender of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	52	65.0	65.0
Female	28	35.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: primary source, 2022

Table 4.1.1 indicates that 65% of the respondents were Male and 35% were female. This means that the majority of the respondents are male whereas the minority is Female.

Table: 4.1.2 Age of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
20-30	59	73.8	73.8
31-43	16	20.0	93.8
44 and above	5	6.3	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

According to Table 4.1.2 the majority of the respondents 73.8% were between 20-30 years old, 20% were between 31-43 years old while 6.3 % were 44 years and above. This means that the Age Group of 20-30 is the majority whereas the other age groups are minority.

Table: 4.1.3: Marital status of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Single	58	72.5	72.5
Married	22	27.5	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 4.1.3 indicates demographics in marital status characteristics, and the result showed that 72.5% of respondents were single while 27.5% of the respondents were married. So the Majority of the respondents are single.

Table: 4.1.4: Educational level of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Bachelor	54	67.5	67.5
Master	19	23.8	91.3
PHD	7	8.8	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 4.1.4 classified the levels of education of respondent into three parts. And the result showed that 67.5% of the respondents had bachelor, 23.8% of the respondents had master degree, while 8.8% of the respondents had PHD. So the majority of the respondents had bachelor.

Table: 4.1.5: Experience level of the respondents

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
less than one year	26	32.5	32.5
1 to 2 years	18	22.5	55.0
2 to 3 years	20	25.0	80.0
4 years and above	16	20.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 4.1.5 summarizes demographics in level of experience characteristics, and the result showed that 32.5% of the respondents had less than one year, 25% of the respondents had 2 to 3 years, and 22.5% had 1 to 2 years while 20% respondents had 4 years and above experience.

4.2 To find out the role of social media on promoting political accountability in Somalia.

Table: 4.2.1 Social media provide an opportunity to foster the transparency of governments and to strengthen the interaction between citizens and government.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	10	12.5	12.5
Disagree	5	6.3	18.8
Neutral	12	15.0	33.8
Agree	37	46.3	80.0
Strongly agree	16	20.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

According to Table 4.2.1 the majority of the respondents 46.3% agreed, 20% strongly agreed it, 15% were neutral, 12.5% strongly disagreed, while 6.3 % disagreed it. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.2.2 Social media provides citizens information useful for evaluating the performance of governments.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	6	7.5	7.5
Disagree	7	8.8	16.3
Neutral	12	15.0	31.3
Agree	39	48.8	80.0
Strongly agree	16	20.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 48.8% were answered agree that Social media provides citizens information useful for evaluating the performance of governments, 20% were answered strongly agree, 15% were answered neutral, 8.8% were answered disagree while 7.5% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.2.3 Social media has great role in promoting political accountability

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	5	6.3	6.3
Disagree	7	8.8	15.0
Neutral	11	13.8	28.8
Agree	39	48.8	77.5
Strongly agree	18	22.5	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 48.8% were answered agree that Social media has great role in promoting political accountability, 22.5% were answered strongly agree, 13.8% were answered neutral, 8.8% were answered disagree while 6.3% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.2.4 Social media is the most reliable Media Platform.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	6	7.5	7.5
Disagree	12	15.0	22.5
Neutral	19	23.8	46.3
Agree	29	36.3	82.5
Strongly agree	14	17.5	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 36.3% were answered agree that Social media is the most reliable Media Platform, 23.8% were answered neutral, 17.5% were answered strongly agree, 15% were answered disagree while 7.5% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.2.5 Social media will replace other kinds of mass media in future.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	2	2.5	2.5
Disagree	6	7.5	10.0
Neutral	14	17.5	27.5
Agree	35	43.8	71.3
Strongly agree	23	28.8	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 43.8% were answered agree that Social media is the most reliable Media Platform, 28.8% were answered strongly agree, 17.5% were answered neutral, 7.5% were answered disagree while only 2.5% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

4.3 To determine the role of Broadcast media on political accountability in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Table: 4.3.1 Broadcast media provide information to public to educate and promote democratic values such as the rule of law, transparency and accountability.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	4	5.0	5.0
Disagree	9	11.3	16.3
Neutral	15	18.8	35.0
Agree	36	45.0	80.0
Strongly agree	16	20.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 45% were answered agree, 20% were answered strongly agree, 18.8% were answered neutral, 11.3% were answered disagree while only 5% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.3.2 Radio is most famous and effective among people in political awareness than T.V, newspaper or other sources of media.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	10	12.5	12.5
Disagree	11	13.8	26.3
Neutral	10	12.5	38.8
Agree	27	33.8	72.5
Strongly agree	22	27.5	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 33.8% were answered agree that Radio is most famous and effective among people in political awareness than T.V, newspaper or other sources of media., transparency and accountability, 27.5% were answered strongly agree, 13.8% were answered disagree, 12.5% were answered neutral while 12.5% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.3.3 Free press and informed citizens can change and retain governments in electoral process.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	5	6.3	6.3
Disagree	8	10.0	16.3
Neutral	16	20.0	36.3
Agree	36	45.0	81.3
Strongly agree	15	18.8	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table shows that 45% were answered agree that Free press and informed citizens can change and retain governments in electoral processes, 20% were answered neutral, 18.8% were answered strongly agree, 10% were answered disagree while only 6.3% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.3.4 Despite the rapid expansion of the Internet, television and radio had maintained their massive appeal to audiences worldwide.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	2	2.5	2.5
Disagree	6	7.5	10.0
Neutral	14	17.5	27.5
Agree	36	45.0	72.5
Strongly agree	22	27.5	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 4.3.4 shows that 45% were answered agree that Despite the rapid expansion of the Internet, television and radio had maintained their massive appeal to audiences worldwide, 27.5% were answered strongly agree, 17.5% were answered neutral, 7.5% were answered disagree while only 2.5% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.3.5 Media is taken as one of the strongest pillars in enforcing and influencing political accountability.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	5	6.3	6.3
Disagree	10	12.5	18.8
Neutral	10	12.5	31.3
Agree	22	27.5	58.8
Strongly agree	33	41.3	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Table 4.3.5 shows that 41.3% were answered strongly agree that Media is taken as one of the strongest pillars in enforcing and influencing political accountability, 27.5% were answered agree, 12.5% were answered neutral, 12.5% were answered disagree while 6.3% were answered strongly disagree. It means majority the majority of the respondents were answered strongly agree.

4.4 To assess ways in which media ownership effects on political accountability.

Table: 4.4.1 Government owned media news is more reliable and accurate than privately owned media.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	17	21.3	21.3
Disagree	25	31.3	52.5
Neutral	14	17.5	70.0
Agree	16	20.0	90.0
Strongly agree	8	10.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table that 31.3% were answered disagree, 21.3% were answered strongly disagree, 20% were answered agree, 17.5% were answered neutral while 10% were answered strongly agree. It means the majority of the respondents were answered disagree.

Table: 4.4.2 Private media have more contribution in promoting accountability rather than government channels.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	4	5.0	5.0
Disagree	14	17.5	22.5
Neutral	12	15.0	37.5
Agree	33	41.3	78.8
Strongly agree	17	21.3	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table and below figure shows that 41.3% were answered agree that Private media have more contribution in promoting accountability rather than government channels, 21.3% were answered strongly agree, 17.5% were answered disagree, 15% were answered neutral while 5% were answered strongly disagree. It means the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.4.3 Media is free and independent in Somalia.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	15	18.8	18.8
Disagree	14	17.5	36.3
Neutral	10	12.5	48.8
Agree	28	35.0	83.8
Strongly agree	13	16.3	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table and below figure shows that 35% were answered agree that Media is free and independent in Somalia, 18.8% were answered strongly disagree, 17.5% were answered disagree, 16.3% were answered strongly agree while 12.5% were answered neutral. It means the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

Table: 4.4.4 Media work for the country not for the owner.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	11	13.8	13.8
Disagree	28	35.0	48.8
Neutral	10	12.5	61.3
Agree	19	23.8	85.0
Strongly agree	12	15.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table and below figure shows that 35% were answered disagree that Media works for the country not for the owner, 23.8% were answered agree, 15% were answered strongly agree, 13.8% were answered strongly disagree while 12.5% were answered neutral. It means the majority of the respondents were answered disagree.

Table: 4.4.5 Public and Private owned Media affects their messages by the Security authorities.

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Strongly disagree	9	11.3	11.3
Disagree	8	10.0	21.3
Neutral	6	7.5	28.8
Agree	37	46.3	75.0
Strongly agree	20	25.0	100.0
Total	80	100.0	

Source: Primary Data, 2022

Above table and below figure shows that 46.3% were answered agree that Public and Private owned Media affects their messages by the Security authorities, 25% were answered strongly agree, 11.3% were answered strongly disagree, 10% were answered disagree while 7.5% were answered neutral. It means the majority of the respondents were answered agree.

4.5 Discussion of the findings

4.5.1 Characteristics of research respondents

This section present the background information of the respondents participate the collection of primary data of the study. The findings of the study showed above in tabular and graphical forms, indicates that the Gender of 65% of the respondent were male, while 35.0% of them were female, The research also showed the age of the respondents 73.8% of the respondents were between 20-30 years, while 20% of respondents are 31- 43 years, and the last 6.3% of respondents are 44 and above years. These results show that the most participants who contributed to get the primary data of this research were 20-30 years. These result also showed that 72% of the respondents were single, while 27.5% of the respondents were married.

4.6 Objectives

4.6.1 The role of social media on political accountability in Somalia.

The first objective of the study was to find out the role of social media on promoting political accountability in Somalia. The results found from the analysis of the respondent's answers Shows that the majority of the respondents 44.8% of the respondents were answered agree, 21.8% strongly agree and 17% neutral while 9.3% and 7.3% were answered disagree and strongly disagree respectively, this means that social media has role in promoting political accountability.

4.6.2 The role of Broadcast media on political accountability in Somalia.

The second objective of the study was to determine the role of Broadcast media on political accountability in Somalia. The results found from the analysis of the respondent's answers indicate that the majority of the respondents 39.3% of the respondents were answered agree, 27% strongly agree and 16.3% neutral while 11% and 6.5% were answered disagree and strongly disagree respectively, this means that broadcast media has role in enhancing accountability.

4.6.3 Ways in which media ownership effects on political accountability.

The third objective of the study was to assess ways in which media ownership effects on political accountability. The results found from the analysis of the respondent's answers indicate that the majority of the respondents 33.3% agree, 22.3% disagree and 17.5% strongly agree while 14% and 13% were answered strongly disagree and neutral respectively, this means that media ownership and independence effects promoting accountability.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.0 Introduction

This Section is the last of the study of the role of mass media on political accountability. it deals with Conclusion and recommendations of the researcher and provides conclusions basing on the findings of objectives, recommendations refer to the solutions produced by the research, and a researcher presents the possible solutions to the research questions based on the findings of the research.

5.1 Conclusion

This study desired to investigate the role mass media on political accountability, to find out the extent or degree of which social media, broadcast media promote political accountability and ways in which media ownership affects political accountability. Media freedom can be fruitful for the promotion of democracy, media and democracy is connected with each other for the development of the country. the researcher proposed the study methodology including research design which was descriptive design, cross sectional data collecting method, questionnaire used for data collecting, target population taken were 100 in number but selected 80 people from them regarding them these who will be asked about study problem. According to the study findings social media play significant role in promoting democracy, it provides opportunity to foster transparency and strength the interaction between citizens and government. And study showed possibility of social media to become alternative of traditional media platforms bridging the gap between citizens and politicians. Findings showed media as one of the most important factors for accountability. According to the third objective of the study ways media ownership effects media accountability the result of the respondents showed that Somalia media is not free and independent from incumbents however Independent, free and fair media is necessary for democracy. Freedom of media is assign of good democracy where media play its role without taking side of any political party. Media role is to dig out the truth and aware people about political condition of the country.

5.2 Recommendations

The following recommendations can be made from this study:

- Study suggests governments to preserve fundamental freedom of media and freedom of information of citizens and make policies that will protect the independence of the media in ensuring strong political accountability in Somalia.
- Social media to be viable alternative of state controlled media; adequate care needs to be taken in order to create an environment in which new technologies can foster citizen empowerment, which in turn will provide good governance and accountability in Somalia.
- People should try as much as possible to use the media channels available to ensure that they benefit a lot from the discussions that take place and that their inputs are also heard.
- Political Pressure to Media: Politicians should decrease their compression and pressure to the media, in order for the relationship between them to be a significant and favorable one.
- suggests the media have a best chance to fulfill their watchdog role and to enforce accountability when supported by the effort of other accountability institutions such as courts

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